

Plant regeneration at different durations in culture of calli derived from young inflorescences and seeds of *O. perennis*^a IRRI, 1987.

Passage (mo in culture)	Young inflorescence-derived callus				Seed-derived callus			
	Calli plated (no.)	Calli responding ^b (%)	Total plants produced (no.)	Av green plant production ^c (no.)	Calli plated (no.)	Calli responding ^b (%)	Total plants produced (no.)	Av green plant production ^c (no.)
6-8	25	80	117	5.8	20	75.0	97	6.5
7-9	20	65	78	6.0	20	50.0	58	5.8
8-10	20	60	62	5.2	15	66.7	60	6.0
9-11	25	60	64	4.3	12	58.3	35	5.0
10-12	20	60	42	3.5	43	69.8	132	4.4
11-13	34	58.8	70	3.5	20	65.0	52	4.0
12-14	34	35.3	43	3.6	20	70.0	57	4.1
13-15	20	40	24	3.0	30	66.7	65	3.3
14-16	20	45	20	2.2	30	53.3	17	1.1

^aComputed after 4 wk in culture on MS₁₈₋₁ medium.

^b $\frac{\text{Total no. calli responding}}{\text{Total no. calli plated for regeneration}} \times 100$

^cPlants produced/calli-producing plant.

This is the first report on somatic embryogenesis from a wild rice species. Young inflorescences and scutellum of mature seeds appear to be appropriate explants for establishing wild rice species plants via somatic embryogenesis. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Trichoderma in Philippine ricefield soils

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Common soil fungus *Trichoderma* can control several soil-borne pathogens. To assess its potential as a biocontrol agent in disease management of crops planted after rainfed rice, we collected 200 soil samples from 23 Philippine provinces Oct 1985 - Dec 1986.

Trichoderma was isolated by dilution plate and soil plate techniques using *Trichoderma* medium E.

Trichoderma populations in 90% of the samples ranged from 0.5 to 8.5 × 10³ CFU/g of soil. The survey recorded 13 species, including 7 new to the Philippines and 2 unidentified.

Dominance and occurrence of species varied with culture type (see table).

Our study showed wide distribution and variation in dominance of different species. All species were antagonistic to rice sheath blight fungus *in vitro*. The potential isolates belonging to different species could be used as biocontrol agents in crop disease management.

Occurrence of *Trichoderma* species in lowland and upland rice fields in the Philippines, 1985-86.

Culture type	Species			
	Dominant 70-40%	Common 20-39%	Uncommon 2-5%	Very rare 1-2%
Upland	<i>T. aureoviride</i> or <i>T. harzianum</i>	<i>T. piluliferum</i> <i>T. fongibrachiatum</i>	<i>T. koningii</i> ^a <i>Trichoderma</i> ^b I <i>Trichoderma</i> ^b II	<i>T. pseudokoningii</i> <i>T. hamatum</i> ^a <i>T. glaucum</i> ^a <i>T. polysporum</i> ^a <i>T. viride</i> ^a <i>T. reesei</i> ^a
Lowland	<i>T. pseudokoningii</i> or <i>T. aureoviride</i>	<i>T. harzianum</i> <i>T. piluliferum</i> ^a <i>T. longibrachiatum</i>	<i>T. koningii</i> <i>Trichoderma</i> sp. I <i>Trichoderma</i> sp. II	<i>T. glaucum</i> <i>T. hamatum</i> <i>T. polysporum</i> <i>T. viride</i> <i>T. reesei</i>

^aSpecies not previously reported in the Philippines. ^bSpecies unidentified.

Interaction *in vivo* between virulent and avirulent cultures of rice bacterial blight (BB) pathogen

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When tested for virulence, some cultures of the BB pathogen *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* failed to cause typical disease symptoms in the leaves of susceptible variety TN1. The cultures

induced only dark brown discoloration at inoculated sites. Microscopic examination did not reveal characteristic bacterial streaming in those leaves.

The cultures were identified as avirulent (AV) forms of the bacterium. The AV cultures were morphologically and culturally identical to virulent (V) cultures except that they grew faster on culture medium.

We studied the interaction between V and AV cultures on TN1 plants.

Standard aqueous suspensions of